

USING A HOMOGENIZATION PROCEDURE FOR PREDICTION OF MATERIAL PROPERTIES AND THE IMPACT RESPONSE OF UNIDIRECTIONAL COMPOSITE

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SUMMARY: The aim of the work is to design hierarchical model for description of the dynamic behaviour of unidirectional composite. On the basis of the Maxwell-type viscoelastic model [1] a procedure of derivation of dynamic equations for the composites is proposed. The space arrangement of constituents in the direction transversally to the symmetry axis is out of consideration. In the present paper the bonding between the constituents is assumed to be perfect. Comparing data of the known theories and experiments with the results obtained, the effective elastic characteristics are in good agreement for fibrous composites, and are coincident with the known theory [2] for laminated composites. Assuming finite elastic deformations, the procedure gives the equations containing the well-known plastic spin. The model obtained is applied to the problem of the shock-wave propagation in an obliquely loaded laminated composite. The shock-wave splitting is observed that is in agreement with the experiment [3]. The phenomenon is explained by analysis of peculiarities of the load-deformation curve. The cause is seen in the variation of the strength properties of the composite due to the reinforcement rotation during the loading.

KEYWORDS: hierarchical model, homogenization approach, shock-wave propagation, off-axis loading, laminated composite

INTRODUCTION

Practical needs in the consideration of composite as a homogeneous anisotropic medium gave a rise in popularity of homogenization procedures. This consideration provides quite correct general description of the process of loading. Simple homogenization rules work quite well in numerous applications and they are very convenient for the finite-element computations of structures containing composite members. However, in some cases the micromechanical peculiarities are of interest and description of residual stresses and internal microstresses is required.

Micromechanical approaches give a useful information but they are restricted to the consideration of individual fibre [2, 4-6]. Therefore, the homogenization approach is best suited for an analysis the composite as a whole. Most of the known procedures aim to derive

elastic moduli of composite in order to use the anisotropic theory of elasticity in finite element computations.

Our objective is to design a procedure for derivation of evolution equations. In doing so the effective elastic characteristics are a by-product. Three-level hierarchy is established during the application of the procedure. The low level is associated with the microstructural process in the composite's constituents (irreversible processes in the lattice caused by dislocations and microdefects). In the paper this level is realized by the description of the constituents by the Maxwell-type viscoelastic model [1]. The second level is associated with the micromechanics of the composite and results from the description of the fibre-matrix interaction. Finally, the upper level is presented by the description of the composite as a whole (the phenomenological description) within the framework of the conservation laws and constitutive equations; these latter are derived from the basic model (the low level) and the homogenization procedure (the second level).

The resultant equations can also be used in the finite element computations. An application of the model to the three-point bending problem is presented in the proceedings [7]. The Onsager principle, expressing the symmetry of inelastic reactions to the load, is valid for the model. This principle is of fundamental significance for the design of finite-element algorithm because it enables one to derive the symmetrical stiffness matrix.

THE HOMOGENIZATION APPROACH: BRIEF DESCRIPTION

Homogenization procedure has to take into consideration a great number of factors. The composite is a very complex structure and the interaction between components is hard to analyse. Therefore, a certain degree of idealisation is necessary to describe both the composite as a whole and at least the main features of the constituents' interaction.

The main problem in the design of the phenomenological theories is to take into consideration as many factors as possible and to make the derivation as simple and utilitarian as possible. As a basis, we take quite complex model for the description of the constituents. This gives us some reserve in manipulation by assumptions of the second level. Because the utility of derivation and thermodynamical correctness of the model are among our aims, we select a simple set of assumptions for the description of the constituents' interaction.

Due to the presupposed perfect bonding of components the equality of velocities in the fibres and matrix is the case. The load transfer between the components is quite complex and depends on the length and quality of fibres. Distribution of radial and circumferential stresses around fibre and the interaction of the stress fields among individual fibres and matrix are also nontrivial issues in the micromechanics of composites. Taking as an example the fibrous unidirectional composite, we consider that the following assumptions are absolutely necessary: i) the difference between the constituents' stresses in direction of the fibre line can not be neglected; ii) this difference induces internal microstresses acting in the longitudinal direction. For simplifying assumptions we take: i) stresses in the transversal direction are distributed uniformly in both composite's components; ii) the mixture rule for stresses in the longitudinal direction is valid. Mathematical representation of the assumptions stated above is:

$$\sigma_{ij}^{(1)} = \sigma_{ij}^{(2)} = \sigma_{ij}, \quad (i, j) \neq (1,1) \quad (1)$$

Here the x_1 - direction is assumed to be coincident with the fibre direction, the stresses inside fibres are $\sigma_{ij}^{(1)}$, inside matrix - $\sigma_{ij}^{(2)}$, 'averaged' stresses of the composite as a whole - σ_{ij} . Hereafter, the upper indices in parentheses are associated with the number of a composite's constituent ("1" - fibre, "2" - matrix). It is assumed that only the difference between $\sigma_{11}^{(1)}$ and $\sigma_{11}^{(2)}$ can not be neglected. This difference generates internal microstresses determined by variable Δ_{11} that presents the difference between elastic microstrains $\varepsilon_{11}^{(1)}$ and $\varepsilon_{11}^{(2)}$:

$$\Delta_{11} = \varepsilon_{11}^{(1)} - \varepsilon_{11}^{(2)}. \quad (2)$$

Connection with the internal microstresses is obvious because microstresses $\sigma_{ij}^{(k)}$ are related to elastic microstrains $\varepsilon_{ij}^{(k)}$ by the Hooke's law. An interesting peculiarity of this structural parameter is that it is irreducible at elastic deformations of the composite as a whole including the stress release. Therefore, Δ_{11} is connected directly with the residual stresses in the composite.

On the microlevel the longitudinal stress σ_{11} is a sum of the longitudinal microstresses $\sigma_{ij}^{(k)}$ proportionally to the fibre volume fraction c :

$$\sigma_{11} = c\sigma_{11}^{(1)} + (1-c)\sigma_{11}^{(2)} \quad (3)$$

Thus, this procedure avoids the fibre arrangement, the component's bonding and local distributions of the transverse stresses but enables the longitudinal microstresses to be taken into account. Additional hypotheses for elastic microstrains and thermophysical variables (temperature T and specific entropy s) are:

$$T = T^{(1)} = T^{(2)}, \quad s = cs^{(1)} + (1-c)s^{(2)}, \quad (4)$$

$$\varepsilon_{11} = \varepsilon_{11}^{(1)} - \bar{\varepsilon}_{11}^{(1)}, \quad (5)$$

$$\varepsilon_{ij} = c(\varepsilon_{ij}^{(1)} - \bar{\varepsilon}_{ij}^{(1)}) + (1-c)(\varepsilon_{ij}^{(2)} - \bar{\varepsilon}_{ij}^{(2)}), \quad (i, j) \neq (1,1), \quad (6)$$

here $\bar{\varepsilon}_{ij}^{(k)}$ - microstrains induced in the constituents by the irreversible processes after the stress release has occurred.

The origin of the least obvious hypothesis (5) results from the micromechanical consideration of the loading-unloading cycle of unidirectional composite in the longitudinal direction. A detailed analysis and derivation of (5) have been carried out in [8]. Absolutely similar hypotheses are constructed for the unidirectional laminated composite.

Introduction of the assumptions for microstrains and temperature gives an opportunity to connect all microstresses, microstrains and corresponding thermophysical characteristics to the macrovariables. If the equations of dynamic behaviour for each the composite's components are given, then, using the hypotheses stated above, we can obtain: i) relationships between stresses and strains (including the temperature and entropy); ii) equations of the dynamics of composite.

Detailed derivation for the case of small elastic deformations is stated for the unidirectional fibrous and laminated composites in [8,9]. Generalisation for the case of finite elastic deformations is based on the use of a transformation of a rectangular system associated with fibre into the Cartesian coordinate system. In fact, the transformation is a matrix of the fibre rotation and it determines fibre location in the stress release state.

The transformation of the tensor variables (strains, stresses, the structural parameter Δ) results in the appearance of the plastic spin in the right-hand sides, which are responsible for the inelastic behaviour of composite. In general form the system of equations of the model is:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{da_{ij}}{dt} + a_{ik} \frac{\partial u_k}{\partial x_j} &= -a_{ik} \psi_{kj}, & \frac{db_{ij}}{dt} &= \theta_{ik} b_{kj}, \\ \frac{d\Delta_{ij}}{dt} &= -\lambda_{ij} + \theta_{ik} \Delta_{kj} - \Delta_{ik} \theta_{kj}, \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{\psi}_{11} &= \alpha_{11} \tilde{\sigma}_{11} + \alpha_{12} \tilde{\sigma}_{22} + \alpha_{12} \tilde{\sigma}_{33} + \beta_1 \tilde{q}, \\ \tilde{\psi}_{22} &= \alpha_{12} \tilde{\sigma}_{11} + \alpha_{22} \tilde{\sigma}_{22} + \alpha_{23} \tilde{\sigma}_{33} + \beta_2 \tilde{q}, \\ \tilde{\psi}_{33} &= \alpha_{12} \tilde{\sigma}_{11} + \alpha_{23} \tilde{\sigma}_{22} + \alpha_{22} \tilde{\sigma}_{33} + \beta_2 \tilde{q}, \\ \tilde{\psi}_{ij} &= \alpha_{66} \tilde{\sigma}_{ij}, \quad \tilde{\lambda}_{11} = \beta_1 \tilde{\sigma}_{11} + \beta_2 \tilde{\sigma}_{22} + \beta_2 \tilde{\sigma}_{33} + \gamma \tilde{q}, \quad i \neq j \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

here $\alpha_{ij}, \beta, \gamma$ - the coefficients derived by use of the homogenization procedure from the functions of the Maxwell-type model for the composite's components [9], they depend on the relaxation functions and the stress state in the constituents. The symmetry of coefficients in (8) expresses the fundamental fact - the Onsager symmetry principle. In the system (7) θ_{ij} are components of a tensor which is responsible for irreversible change in the fibre orientation, it is a given function when the functions $\tilde{\psi}_{ij}$ are given. The tensor with components b_{ij} is a tensor of irreversible rotation for fibre, $\tilde{q} = E_{\tilde{\Delta}}$, a tilde-variable \tilde{f}_{ij} is a tensor in the rectangular system associated with either the fibre or the normal to lamina, it is expressed through that in the Cartesian system by the standard transformation rule: $f_{ij} = b_{ik} \tilde{f}_{km} b_{mj}$. The system (7) is completed by the conservation laws for energy and momentum, and a given dependence of the internal energy E on the strain tensor, structural parameter and entropy.

EFFECTIVE ELASTIC CHARACTERISTICS

To illustrate the influence of the fibre content on elastic moduli, the characteristics in this section will be analysed for the case of isothermal deformation. Invoking the procedure of homogenization, the Hooke's laws for constituents yield the stress-strain relations which are typical for the transversely isotropic material:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \sigma_{11} &= C_{11}\varepsilon_{11} + C_{12}\varepsilon_{22} + C_{12}\varepsilon_{33}, \\
 \sigma_{22} &= C_{12}\varepsilon_{11} + C_{22}\varepsilon_{22} + C_{23}\varepsilon_{33}, \\
 \sigma_{33} &= C_{12}\varepsilon_{11} + C_{23}\varepsilon_{22} + C_{22}\varepsilon_{33}, \quad \sigma_{ij} = 2C_{66}\varepsilon_{ij}, \quad i \neq j
 \end{aligned} \tag{9}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned}
 C_{11} &= \langle \lambda + 2\mu \rangle + \left\langle \frac{\lambda}{\lambda + \mu} \right\rangle^2 \left\langle \frac{1}{\lambda + \mu} \right\rangle^{-1} - \left\langle \frac{\lambda^2}{\lambda + \mu} \right\rangle, \quad C_{12} = \left\langle \frac{\lambda}{\lambda + \mu} \right\rangle \left\langle \frac{1}{\lambda + \mu} \right\rangle^{-1}, \\
 C_{22} &= \left\langle \frac{1}{\lambda + \mu} \right\rangle^{-1} + \left\langle \frac{1}{\mu} \right\rangle^{-1}, \quad C_{23} = \left\langle \frac{1}{\lambda + \mu} \right\rangle^{-1} - \left\langle \frac{1}{\mu} \right\rangle^{-1}, \\
 C_{66} &= \frac{1}{2}(C_{22} - C_{23}) = \left\langle \frac{1}{\mu} \right\rangle^{-1},
 \end{aligned} \tag{10}$$

here λ, μ are the Lamé coefficients. Expressions in the angle parentheses present the mixture rule $\langle K \rangle = cK_2 + (1-c)K_1$. $\langle K \rangle = cK_2 + (1-c)K_1$. The longitudinal and transverse Young's moduli E_1, E_2 , the shear modulus G_2 and the longitudinal and transverse Poisson's coefficients ν_1, ν_2 can be easily linked with C_{ij} :

$$\begin{aligned}
 E_1 &= \frac{2C_{12}^2}{C_{22} + C_{23}}, \quad E_2 = \frac{(C_{22} - C_{23})[C_{11}(C_{22} + C_{23}) - 2C_{12}^2]}{(C_{11}C_{22} - C_{12}^2)}, \\
 G_2 &= C_{66}, \quad \nu_1 = \frac{C_{12}}{C_{22} + C_{23}}, \quad \nu_2 = \frac{C_{11}C_{23} - C_{12}^2}{C_{11}C_{22} - C_{12}^2}.
 \end{aligned} \tag{11}$$

It is interesting to note that the procedure applied to the laminated structure gives the elastic moduli which coincide identically with those stated in the popular monography by Christensen [2]. Therefore, we shall analyse the dependencies of the elastic constants on the fibre content only for the fibrous composite.

The well-known estimates for an effective modulus of the composite K_c (K_f - the respective elastic modulus of fibres, K_m - the elastic modulus of matrix) are the Voigt estimate (the mixture rule) and the Reuss estimate, respectively:

$$K_c = cK_f + (1-c)K_m, \quad 1/K_c = c/K_f + (1-c)/K_m,$$

where c - the fibre volume concentration.

The longitudinal Young's modulus E_1 for the composite in most of theories is in very good agreement with the Voigt estimate (the rule of mixture), experiments are in agreement with this rule, too. Our formulas are not an exclusion and they are practically coincident with the linear dependence of the mixture rule.

Fig. 1: The transversal Young's modulus (a) and the rigidity modulus (b) for the glass/epoxy fibrous composite

Theoretical and experimental dependencies are not so simple for the transversal Young's modulus E_2 and the rigidity modulus G_2 . The well-known approximation for the moduli is the Reuss estimate. It is interesting to note that our dependence for the rigidity modulus is exactly the Reuss estimate. Experiments stated in [4] give the moduli (points in Fig. 1) for the glass/epoxy composite (elastic constants for fibre and matrix are $E_f = 731 \text{ GPa}$, $G_f = 302 \text{ GPa}$, $\nu_f = 0.22$, $E_m = 3.45 \text{ GPa}$, $G_m = 1.8 \text{ GPa}$, $\nu_m = 0.35$). Our results (curves 1 according to equations (10), (11)) are compared in Fig. 1 with the theory of [4] and the Reuss estimate of the effective moduli. It is seen that the discrepancy between all the theories and experiment is of the same order.

Experimental data for the graphite/epoxy-resin composite by Goggin [10] are stated by points in Fig. 2. Elastic data for the constituents are: the type 1 fibre $E_f = 395 \text{ GPa}$, $\nu_f = 0.28$; the type 2 fibre $E_f = 230 \text{ GPa}$, $\nu_f = 0.28$; the fibre in the transversal direction: $E_f = 276 \text{ GPa}$, $\nu_f = 0.28$; the epoxy resin system: $E_m = 3.9 \text{ GPa}$, $\nu_m = 0.33$. Fig. 2, (a) corresponds to the transversal Young's modulus E_1 , Fig. 2, (b) - the rigidity modulus G_2 , Fig. 2, (c,d) - the longitudinal and transversal Poisson's ratios ν_1 and ν_2 , respectively. Curves 1, 2, 3 in Fig. 2, (a) correspond to the three types of fibres mentioned above according to the formulas (10), (11), curve 1 in Fig. 2, (b-d) - to the fibre type 1 calculated by the same formula.

The data by Goggin have quite large scatter, especially for the Poisson's ratio. The Young's modulus of the fibre type 2 is less than that of the fibre type 1. However, the transverse Young's modulus of the composite with the fibre type 2 is higher than that with the fibre type 1 (Fig. 2, (2)). Apparently, this feature is associated with the strong anisotropic properties of fibres. Our model of the constituents is an isotropic material. Therefore, we calculated curve 3 in Fig. 2 (a) for a fibre with the Young's modulus corresponding to the experimental transversal Young's modulus of the graphite fibre.

Among theoretical data the well-known formulae are those by R. Hill stated in [5]. For the constants from (10) they take the form:

$$C_{11} = \langle \lambda + 2\mu \rangle - c(1-c) \frac{(\lambda_1 - \lambda_2)^2}{\hat{\lambda} + \hat{\mu} + M}, \quad C_{12} = \langle \lambda \rangle - c(1-c) \frac{(\lambda_1 - \lambda_2)(\lambda_1 + \mu_1 - \lambda_2 - \mu_2)}{\hat{\lambda} + \hat{\mu} + M},$$

$$C_{66} = \frac{1}{2}(C_{22} - C_{23}) = \langle \mu \rangle - c(1-c) \frac{(\mu_1 - \mu_2)^2}{\hat{\mu} + M}, \quad (12)$$

$$\frac{1}{2}(C_{22} + C_{23}) = \langle \lambda + \mu \rangle - c(1-c) \frac{(\lambda_1 + \mu_1 - \lambda_2 - \mu_2)^2}{\hat{\lambda} + \hat{\mu} + M},$$

here $\hat{f} = (1-c)f_1 + cf_2$. It is easy to check that at $M=0$ these formulæ reduce to dependencies (10). Because M has the meaning of the shear modulus we take as an example $M = \langle \mu \rangle$. Calculations according to (12) give the curve 4 in Fig.2, (a) and curves 3 in Fig. 2, (c-d). The semi-empirical dependencies by C.Chamis stated in [6] are the curve 5 in Fig. 2, (a) and curves 2 in Fig. 2, (b-d). Our formulæ describe experiments on the Poisson's ratio in the best way among theoretical data mentioned above. For the transversal Young's modulus and the rigidity modulus the discrepancy between all the theories and experiment is again of the same order.

Fig. 2: The effective elastic characteristics for the graphite/epoxy composite. The transversal Young's modulus (a) (points are the experiments [10]); the rigidity modulus (b); the longitudinal Poisson's ratio (c); the transversal Poisson's ratio (d)

The comparison gives us a confidence in use of the homogenization approach for the derivation of dynamic equations.

THE SHOCK WAVE RESPONSE OF COMPOSITE

To illustrate the potential of the model a computation of the shock wave propagation in obliquely oriented laminated composite has been conducted. The method of calculation of the system (7) is the finite-difference Godunov scheme. The composite structure has been chosen in accordance with an experimental sample by Sve and Okubo [3], where the Al/Lexan composite has been oriented symmetrically (Fig. 3,a) and obliquely (Fig. 3, b) to the shock wave.

Fig. 3: Sketches for the straightward and oblique shock-wave loading of the laminated composite

In order to understand the process of the off-axis loading let us consider the loading of the representative volume of the composite by uniaxial stress. The sketch of the process is drawn in Fig. 4. The corresponding load-deformation curve computed by the model shows that in certain range of orientations the stress response is complex due to rearrangement of the composite structure during the loading. At the symmetrical loadings (the cases 1 and 3) the composite strengths correspond to those of the fibre or matrix. For the off-axis loading (the case 2) the composite strength changes during the deformation, depending on the reinforcement direction.

Fig. 4: Schemes of the off-axis loading and calculation of the load-deformation curve for the case of rotation of the reinforcement

Coefficients α, β, γ of the functions ψ_{ij} in (8) which are responsible for the inelastic behaviour of the constituents are constructed from experimental dependencies of the yield limit on the strain rate. The method for the construction of the functions can be found in [11].

Fig. 5: Calculation of the shock-wave response of the symmetry-oriented and obliquely oriented laminated composite; 1 - the velocity profile, 2 - the microstress profile, 3 - the change in the fibre orientation

The shock-wave propagation calculated for the samples in Fig. 3 has a number of peculiarities. At symmetrical loading (velocity versus coordinate in the sample at a moment of time - the curve 1, Fig. 5, a), the fibre orientation does not change during the process (curve 3), $\tilde{\Delta}$ (curve 2) associated with the internal microstress (the difference in elastic strains between the constituents) changes only after the elastic wave has passed and the plastic wave has induced the microstress in the sample.

However, in the case of off-axis loading (the orientation angle $\varphi_0 = 47^\circ$) the fibre orientation becomes an essential factor due to the rearrangement stated in Fig. 4. Initially, the elastic wave acts as in the preceding case (velocity - curve 1 in Fig. 5, b), then the successive load changes the layer orientation and modifies the strength properties of the sample. It is seen from Fig. 5, (b) that in the second wave the angle orientation has been changed (curve 3), a rise in $\tilde{\Delta}$ (curve 2) indicates that the composite in these points is out of elastic range and the change is associated with the structural rearrangement. The third wave performs the final loading up to the limit determined by the striker.

Fig. 6: Comparison between the calculated (curve 1) and the experimental [3] (curve 2) velocity profiles

The comparison of the calculation with the experiments [3] shows good agreement between the velocity profiles (Fig. 6).

CONCLUSION

A homogenization procedure for unidirectional composite is proposed in the paper. The aim of the approach is to design a three-level hierarchical model for description of the dynamic behaviour of the composite materials. Effective elastic characteristics obtained by the procedure for the fibrous and laminated composite are within the range of the well-known theoretical and experimental data. The model is suitable for description of the shock-wave data for composites. The calculation of the obliquely loaded composite is in good agreement with the known experiment [3].

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